

Mechatronics-based Waste Collection and Disposal System

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Abstract:- Waste collection system driven by Artificial Intelligence and Robotics is sine qua non to having a smart city. Unlike the traditional waste collection systems which have been largely ineffective due to lack of technological advancement and increasing growing population, the proposed system provides more efficiency and timeliness in waste collection and disposal, giving room for less lacuna for waste bin overflows. The Bin is based on the concept of mechatronics, which empowers it with sensors, and robotic control systems that is capable of detecting the status of the waste bin, and automatically moves it to the disposal center whenever it is filled up. The mechatronic waste bin consist of rover wheels which allows the bin to move around uneven roads and terrains, each wheel has a DC motor, Digital servo, RC Transmitter, a sensor camera, a PCB, and an Arduino mega board. The sensor monitors the bin and gives an alarm signal to the controller. If the bin is filled up, it covers itself automatically, and moves to a nearby dump with the aid of the Dc motors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mr. TetsuroMoria, a senior engineer of a Japanese company, Yaskawa, first coined the word “Mechatronics” in 1969.

Mechatronics is the synergistic combination of Mechanical engineering (“mecha” for mechanisms), Electronic engineering (“tronics” for electronics) and software engineering.

It is a multi-disciplinary approach to product and manufacturing system design. It involves application of electrical, mechanical, control and computer engineering to develop products, processes and systems with greater flexibility, ease in redesign and ability of reprogramming.

Mechatronics can also be termed as replacement of mechanics with electronics or enhance mechanics with electronics. With the help of microelectronics and sensor technology, mechatronics systems are providing high levels of precision and reliability.

Today’s domestic washing machines are “intelligent” and four-wheel passenger automobiles are equipped with safety installations such as airbags, parking (proximity) sensors, antitheft electronic keys etc.^{[1][2]}

A. Objectives of Mechatronics system

- Integration of mechanical systems with electronic and computer systems
- To improve efficiency of the system
- To reduce cost of production
- To achieve high accuracy and precision
- For easy control of the system
- Customer satisfaction and comfort

B. Relevance of the Proposed System

Recently, we experience waste bins in abandonment due to lack of effective waste collections, man power, lack of timely monitoring and disposal, and further spreading of diseases, pandemics and other airborne diseases due to decay. The proposed system is a mechatronic based waste bin, designed to monitor its fill level, and trigger movement to deliver itself to a nearby waste dump site with or without human intervention.^[3]

This ensures cleanliness in the environment, safety of residents in the particular environment, mechanization, automation and computerization of waste bins, which is sine qua non to having a smart city.

In addition, having a waste bin deliver quality services with artificial intelligence and other concepts that make up mechatronics is worthy of development and implementation.

II. RELATED WORKS

The combination of mechanical and electrical engineering with computer programming, mechatronics is increasingly everywhere. The following are some famous inventions as a result of application of mechatronics:^{[4][5][6]}

A. Sophia the Robot

Developed by Hanson Robotics, Sophia is one of the most famous robots in the world for her interactions with people based on an artificial intelligence. She’s become an ambassador for AI, with her creators exploring and pushing the boundaries of that new technology every day. But did you know that Sophia also uses mechatronics to operate? She moves, talks, and needs power to run in addition to that famous computer brain. According to her, “I... have IK solvers and path planning for controlling my hands, gaze, and locomotion strategy. My walking body performs dynamic stabilization for adaptive walking over various terrain.”

Sophia's social skills would be less impressive if she didn't understand that she should look at you by tilting her head, or that she should move her mouth according to the timing of her speech. She chooses to send power to various parts of her body to move when her programming tells her to, or in other words, she functions via mechatronics.

B. NASA's Curiosity Rover

"In some sense, the Mars Science Laboratory rover's parts are similar to what any living creature would need to keep it "alive" and able to explore," says NASA. They describe Curiosity as having a computer brain, a battery and power for energy, and wheels for mobility. It can also move its arm and hand to collect samples and analyze its environment and communicate with NASA back on Earth with further instruments on board. [7]

C. Anti-lock Brakes

This is one we bet you didn't think of, but mechatronics engineers are responsible for a lot of the functions of your car. Anti-lock braking systems, or ABS, work via sensors that detect the speed of your wheels in addition to an algorithm that tells the car when your wheels are turning faster even though you are trying to brake. When your wheels lock up the ABS activates and tries to keep your wheels from skidding while you slow down. It lets you continue to be able to steer the car while it helps you stop.

"The ABS controller knows that such a rapid deceleration is impossible, so it reduces the pressure to that brake until it sees acceleration, then it increases the pressure

A. DC Motor

A **DC motor** is any of a class of rotary electrical motors that converts direct current (DC) electrical energy

Fig. 1: Dc Motor

B. The Digital RC Servo

A digital servo receives a signal from the receiver onboard the RC vehicle and translates this in to a pulse sent to the servo motor. The rate at which pulses of power are

sent to the servo motor are much higher. You can expect that a digital servo would send a pulse to the servo motor at a rate of 500hz. This is equivalent to every 0.002 seconds.

D. i-Limb

Biomechatronics is a newer field, but a fascinating one. Mechatronics engineers are making machines to support, or in the case of a loss to replace, the natural functions of the human body. One of the most sophisticated examples of this today is i-Limb, a prosthetic hand with bionic components to aid amputees. i-Limb uses sensors placed on the wearer's skin that allow them to control the movement of the hand and fingers through muscle signals. Each finger has its own motor so that wearers can move every part of the hand in a way that mimics the body's natural motor control. [8][9][10]

III. COMPONENTS

The materials required for the design and implementation of the mechatronics-based waste collection and disposal system are as follows:

- DC motor
- Digital servo
- RC Transmitter
- d.Sensor camera,
- PCB
- Arduino mega board.

into mechanical energy. The most common types rely on the forces produced by magnetic fields.

Fig. 2: Digital RC Servo

C. RC Transmitter

The transmitter is essentially the controller that you hold when using the vehicle. It is also referred to as a radio controller or a remote controller. You then make your commands via buttons, dials, and other features and the data is sent to the receiver. The receiver itself is connected to the

vehicle, and uses this information to power the vehicle and turn the wheels (or equivalent) for turning and maneuvering.

RC transmitters are, therefore, one of the most important features of any RC cart setup. They connect to the receiver via a 2.4GHz radio transmission. Once the link is made, it cannot be disrupted by external radio frequencies. ^{[11][12][13][14]}

Fig. 3: RC Transmitter

D. CIRCUIT BOARD DESIGN

Fig. 4: Circuit Board Design

• Architecture of modern automation systems with sensors, actuators, and controllers

Fig. 5: Architecture of modern automation systems with sensors, actuators, and controllers

• **How the system works**

Fig. 6: Data Flow Diagram of the proposed system

Fig. 7: Sample chassis of the Mechatronic based waste collection

E. ADVANTAGES OF THE NEW SYSTEM

- Increased technology, functionality and better designed waste collection
- Use of artificial intelligence and intelligent process control
- Assume responsibility for a process and operation with little interference of operators
- Multisensory and programmed environments
- High degree of flexibility
- Greater productivity and more effective waste collection solution
- The integration of sensor and control system in a complex system reduces capital expenses

F. DISADVANTAGES

- The initial cost is very high
- The complicated design and system
- The repair and maintenance is complex
- Its replacement is difficult, that it is difficult to change old system to new system.
- Imperative to have knowledge of different engineering fields for design and implementation
- Specific problem of various systems will have to be addressed separately and properly^{[15][16][17][18][19][20]}

G. Arduino DC Motor Control

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sketch_aug28a | Arduino 1.8.19
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

sketch_aug28a $
/* Arduino DC Motor Control
  Mechatronics based waste collection and disposal system
  by Dr. Onyedinna, Ese Daniel Uzoma
  */

#define enA 9
#define in1 4
#define in2 5
#define enB 10
#define in3 6
#define in4 7

int motorSpeedA = 0;
int motorSpeedB = 0;

void setup() {
  pinMode(enA, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(enB, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(in1, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(in2, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(in3, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(in4, OUTPUT);
}

Compiling sketch...

Done compiling.
Sketch uses 2674 bytes (1%) of program storage space. Maximum is 253952 bytes.
Global variables use 13 bytes (0%) of dynamic memory, leaving 8179 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 8192 bytes.

sketch_aug28a | Arduino 1.8.19
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

sketch_aug28a $
void loop() {
  int xAxis = analogRead(A0); // Read Joysticks X-axis
  int yAxis = analogRead(A1); // Read Joysticks Y-axis

  // Y-axis used for forward and backward control
  if (yAxis < 470) {
    // Set Motor A backward
    digitalWrite(in1, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(in2, LOW);
    // Set Motor B backward
    digitalWrite(in3, HIGH);
    digitalWrite(in4, LOW);
    // Convert the declining Y-axis readings for going backward from 470 to 0 into 0 to 255 value for the PWM signal for increasing the motor speed
    motorSpeedA = map(yAxis, 470, 0, 0, 255);
    motorSpeedB = map(yAxis, 470, 0, 0, 255);
  }
  else if (yAxis > 550) {
    // Set Motor A forward
    digitalWrite(in1, LOW);
    digitalWrite(in2, HIGH);
    // Set Motor B forward
    digitalWrite(in3, LOW);
    digitalWrite(in4, HIGH);
    // Convert the increasing Y-axis readings for going forward from 550 to 1023 into 0 to 255 value for the PWM signal for increasing the motor speed
  }

  Done compiling.
Sketch uses 2674 bytes (1%) of program storage space. Maximum is 253952 bytes.
Global variables use 13 bytes (0%) of dynamic memory, leaving 8179 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 8192 bytes.

sketch_aug28a | Arduino 1.8.19
File Edit Sketch Tools Help

sketch_aug28a $
  motorSpeedA = map(yAxis, 550, 1023, 0, 255);
  motorSpeedB = map(yAxis, 550, 1023, 0, 255);
}
// If joystick stays in middle the motors are not moving
else {
  motorSpeedA = 0;
  motorSpeedB = 0;
}

// X-axis used for left and right control
if (xAxis < 470) {
  // Convert the declining X-axis readings from 470 to 0 into increasing 0 to 255 value
  int xMapped = map(xAxis, 470, 0, 0, 255);
  // Move to left - decrease left motor speed, increase right motor speed
  motorSpeedA = motorSpeedA - xMapped;
  motorSpeedB = motorSpeedB + xMapped;
  // Confine the range from 0 to 255
  if (motorSpeedA < 0) {
    motorSpeedA = 0;
  }
  if (motorSpeedB > 255) {
    motorSpeedB = 255;
  }
}

Done compiling.
Sketch uses 2674 bytes (1%) of program storage space. Maximum is 253952 bytes.
Global variables use 13 bytes (0%) of dynamic memory, leaving 8179 bytes for local variables. Maximum is 8192 bytes.
    
```

Fig. 8: Arduino DC Motor Code

REFERENCES

- [1.] Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering (9 August 2012). "Mechatronics Engineering". Future undergraduate students. University of Waterloo. Retrieved 21 November 2019.
- [2.] Faculty of Mechatronics, Informatics and Interdisciplinary Studies TUL. "Mechatronics (Bc.,Ing., PhD.)". Retrieved 15 April 2011.
- [3.] Msc. Mechatronics and Automation Engineering, University of Strathclyde Glasgow, Institution of Engineering and Technology, United Kingdom. Retrieved 29 November 2020.
- [4.] Lawrence J. Kamm (1996). *Understanding Electro-Mechanical Engineering: An Introduction to Mechatronics*. John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 978-0-7803-1031-5.
- [5.] Bolton, W. *Mechatronics*. Pearson, 6th edition, 2015. ISBN 9781292076683
- [6.] Bradley, David; Russell, David; Ferguson, Ian (March 2015). "The Internet of Things-The future or the end of mechatronics". *Mechatronics*. 27: 57-74. doi:10.1016/j.mechatronics.2015.
- [7.] L. Atzori, A. Iera and G. Morabito, "The Internet of Things: A survey", *Comput. Netw.*, vol. 54, pp. 2787-2805, Oct. 2010.
- [8.] Meijer and M. P. R. Bolívar, "Governing the smart city: A review of the literature on smart urban governance", *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.*, vol. 82, no. 2, pp. 392-408, 2016.
- [9.] Zanella, N. Bui, A. Castellani, L. Vangelista and M. Zorzi, "Internet of Things for smart cities", *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 22-32, Feb. 2014.
- [10.] N. Misran, M. S. Islam, G. K. Beng, N. Amin and M. T. Islam, "IoT based health monitoring system with LoRa communication technology", *Proc. Int. Conf. Electr. Eng. Informat. (ICEEI)*, pp. 514-517, 2019.
- [11.] M. Shahidul Islam, M. T. Islam, A. F. Almutairi, G. K. Beng, N. Misran and N. Amin, "Monitoring of the human body signal through the Internet of Things (IoT) based LoRa wireless network system", *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 9, pp. 1884, May 2019.
- [12.] S. Sadeq, R. Hassan, S. S. Al-rawi, A. M. Jubair and A. H. M. Aman, "A qos approach for Internet of Things (IoT) environment using mqtt protocol", *Proc. Int. Conf. Cyber Secur.*, pp. 59-63, Sep. 2019.
- [13.] K. S. S. Hulyalkar, R. Deshpande and K. Makode, "Implementation of Smartbin Using Convolutional Neural Networks", *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1-7, 2018.
- [14.] M. S. Medvedev and Y. V. Okuntsev, "Using Google tensorFlow machine learning library for speech recognition", *J. Phys. Conf.*, vol. 1399, Dec. 2019.
- [15.] M. A. Abu, N. H. Indra, A. H. A. Rahman, N. A. Sapiee and I. Ahmad, "A study on image classification based on deep learning and tensorflow", *Int. J. Eng. Res. Technol.*, vol. 12, pp. 563-569, Oct. 2019.
- [16.] Z.-Q. Zhao, P. Zheng, S.-T. Xu and X. Wu, "Object detection with deep learning: A review", *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.*, vol. 30, no. 11, pp. 3212-3232, Nov. 2019.
- [17.] C.-W. Chen, S.-P. Tseng, T.-W. Kuan and J.-F. Wang, "Outpatient text classification using attention-based bidirectional LSTM for robot-assisted servicing in hospital", *Information*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 106, Feb. 2020.
- [18.] H. Yuan, L. Shen and J. Wang, "Major obstacles to improving the performance of waste management in China's construction industry", *Facilities*, vol. 29, no. 5/6, pp. 224-242, Apr. 2011.
- [19.] Prasanna, S. K. Vikash and P. Mahalakshmi, "Survey on identification and classification of waste for efficient disposal and recycling", *Int. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 7, no. 2.8, pp. 520-523, 2018.
- [20.] S. Mdukaza, B. Isong, N. Dladlu and A. M. Abu-Mahfouz, "Analysis of IoT-enabled solutions in smart waste management", *Proc. 44th Annu. Conf. IEEE Ind. Electron. Soc.*, pp. 4639-4644, Oct. 2018.